

THE TYPES OF SOFTWARE FOR EDITING MULTIMEDIA INFORMATION

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ANNOTATION. This article discusses the types of software for editing multimedia information.

Keywords: multimedia, multimedia technologies, multimedia software, multimedia resources, multimedia products, multimedia information visualization.

INTRODUCTION

Modern society actively uses multimedia products. To create such products a wide range of computer software. To work effectively with these softwares, you need to know the features of these tools. Multimedia is content that is presented simultaneously in different forms: sound, animated computer graphics, video. Multimedia is considered a computer technology that allows the presentation of content through a combination of different types of information - both through traditional static information (text, graphics) and through dynamic information (animation, speech, music, video). Multimedia is a single digital space, syncretic representing different ways and types of information presentation. Multimedia is classified as linear, non-linear, hypermedia and live media. To create multimedia products of different classes, different types of software are required. In general, multimedia editors are classified as "Office applications" in the classification of computer programs.

For example, in linear representation, the viewer of a given document cannot influence its output in any way. In a non-linear (interactive) way of presenting information, a person can participate in the output of information by interacting in some way with the means of displaying multimedia data. This process is also called "interactivity". An example for this process is multimedia simulations. A non-linear

way of representing multimedia data is sometimes referred to as "hypermedia". As an example of a linear and non-linear way of presenting information, we can consider the situation associated with the presentation. In MS Power Point presentations, viewers do not have the ability to influence the presenter. In Prezi presentations, the audience has the opportunity to interact with it. Thus, a live presentation can be presented as a non-linear way of presenting information. It can be noted that various forms of providing information make it possible for the consumer to interact interactively with information. Online multimedia is increasingly becoming object-oriented, allowing the consumer to work on information without having specific knowledge. Hypermedia, where the user sees a structure of related media elements and can select them sequentially. In real (live)-multimedia, the user views the content in real time.

Modern multimedia presentations must be more than just a combination of graphics, sound and text. The abundance of entertainment and educational CDs, the growing popularity of business presentations show the impossibility without multimedia in modern times. The high demand for multimedia causes an increase in the requirements for the quality of applications, users need good graphics and high-level interactivity. Media creation tools give users the ability to combine sound and color in ways that do not require knowledge of programming languages. Multimedia application developers need easy-to-use, powerful, and sophisticated tools to create impactful presentations.

RESULTS and DISCUSSIONS

Multimedia finds its application in various fields such as programming, advertising, entertainment, technology, medicine, mathematics, business, scientific research, cartography, art and space-time applications. Various types of software were initially used to create multimedia content: audio editors, programs for photo processing, video editing, 3D modeling, etc. With the development of information technology, developers are working to unify multimedia formats.

The multimedia software consists of three components: system, tool and application software. System software tools - programs that are part of the operating system and control multimedia devices at two levels - physical control of input / output

information at a low level using machine commands (device drivers) and user control of device characteristics using a graphical interface depicting a device control panel , such as adjusting the sound volume, tone, etc. Software tools - programs that allow you to modify multimedia files and create multimedia applications. Programs of this type can be divided into such groups as still image editors, animated GIF creators, audio and video editing tools, presentation tools, text recognition tools entered from a scanner, tutorial creators, voice recognition and conversion systems. sound files to text, systems for creating virtual reality applications and others. Tools provide more control over multimedia devices than is provided by system tools such as professional video editing systems. Application software is ready-made software systems on CD or DVD discs - films, textbooks, encyclopedias, games, books, virtual museums, guides, promotional materials, etc.

There are many software tools for working with multimedia files. Such applications can be divided into several main categories:

- Tools for creating and processing images
- Tools for creating and processing 2D and 3D graphics
- Tools for creating and processing video and animation
- Tools for creating and processing sound
- Tools for creating a presentation

Computer representation of graphic information is implemented using raster or vector graphics. In them, the image is divided into pixels or images are stored as a geometric description of objects. Graphic editors are focused on manipulating existing images and have a set of tools that allow you to correct any aspect of the image. In vector graphics programs, illustration objects and images are created using free-form shapes, their scaling, rotation, deformation, as well as the degree of transparency and color fill. Three-dimensional graphics is implemented by creating object frames, arranging all objects into a single scene, setting lighting and a visualization point - a camera.

For 3D animation, you need to adjust the movement of scene objects and set the number of frames. The movement of objects in three-dimensional space is specified by

trajectories, keyframes, and with the help of formulas that relate the movement of parts of complex structures. After setting the desired motion, lighting and materials, the rendering process starts and a sequence of images is generated. For video editing, there are a large number of software products that allow you to edit multiple video and audio channels and assemble video clips into a single composition and contain sets of transitions between frames, synchronize sound and image, and also support editing and saving the most popular video file formats.

Consider the features of some of the best video editors. VideoMONTAZH is a universal video editor with basic functionality that is suitable for both beginners and professionals. Has features - built-in effects, audio tracks and templates, overlay images or splash screens and edit them, save projects and work with them in the future, more than 100 effects and transitions, works with 50 different formats - for example, AVI, MP4, MOV, MKV, there are opportunities for cropping video, inserting text and graphics, improving images and replacing sound, processes files in resolutions - SD, DVD and Full HD, allows you to work with videos for social networks and video hosting, etc.

Adobe Premiere Pro is a professional video editing software. It has features - designed for editing and creating videos and films, processing special effects and 3D models, more than 1000 standard effects with the ability to additionally download new ones, a built-in audio editor, a convenient work surface where you can compare your video with the original, works with 4K, 8K and VR, mute background noise and sound intensity, import footage in any format, save the frame you like, add animation and video effects, etc.

VEGAS Pro is a video editor for professionals based on artificial intelligence. Used in film studios and television. It has features - a program for working with large projects, a wide range of effects, settings and options for working with video, working with color in HDR, artificial intelligence helps to radically transform the picture and speed up the work process, Open FX plug-ins, interface customization, image stabilizer and video, color correction, built-in audio editor (SOUND FORGE Pro), video noise reduction, work in 4K and 8K, integration with a cloud service, etc.

AVS Video Editor is a simple editing program. It has features - saving files in formats - AVI, DVD, MOV, MP4, MPEG, WMV, MKV, M2TS, TS, GIF, mobile device, more than 300 effects and transitions, recording video in the program from a computer and immediately editing, user-friendly interface, export to social networks, cloud storage and video hosting, video processing in resolutions - HD, Full HD, 2K Quad HD, 4K Ultra HD and DCI 4K, image stabilization, working with color, uploading several videos at once and cutting, etc.

Camtasia Studio is a program for editing webinars, lessons and presentations. It has features - computer screen recording and editing, ready-made templates, a library with music, effects, icons, transitions and various animations, user-friendly interface, export to social networks, video hosting and cloud storage, integration with PowerPoint, audio editor, green background replacement, etc. .d.

Movavi Video Editor is a popular video editor for beginners and professionals. It has features - more than 250 effects and transitions, a library of 40 titles, more than 40 formats for saving files, a user-friendly interface, loading files from various devices - a computer, an external drive, a camera, a TV tuner, 4K support, working with zoom and panorama, sound and audio track editor, stock images and stickers, vertical video fix, new effects and filters download, YouTube and Google Drive integration, etc.

After Effects is a video editor for working with effects and animation. You can make an easy installation. It has features - software for working with animation and VR, a large number of visual effects, titles, transitions and filters, allows you to cut a moving object and move it, work with 3D models, removes and corrects errors in video, allows you to control the weather - add raindrops or flames, image stabilization, creating original titles for videos or films, working with logos, dynamic transitions that allow you to effectively move to the next frame, integration with cloud storage, etc.

In this article, we reviewed video editors and compared their characteristics and came to the conclusion that the best programs that are suitable for beginners and professionals are DaVinci Resolve among free services, and Adobe Premiere Pro, Final Cut Pro X and VEGAS Pro are the best paid ones.

Programs for working with sound can be divided into two large groups: sound editors focused on digital sound recording technologies, and sequencer programs. Sequencers are designed to create music, they are used to encode musical compositions. Sound editors allow you to record sound in real time on a computer hard drive and convert it using the capabilities of digital audio processing and combining different channels. Consider the features of some of the best audio editors.

Sound Forge Pro is an advanced software for musicians and sound engineers. It will completely replace an entire recording studio. You can record music in it on 32 channels simultaneously, and there are many filters and effects for editing, Reads almost all audio formats and some video. It also allows you to work with audio recordings imported from CDs and even cassette media. This music editor's own feature is the ability to download track information from the network. The interface is minimalistic and can be customized according to your preferences. It has a wide range of options for working with sound: recording, processing, mastering, plug-ins.

Audacity is a simple and functional editor that even a beginner can handle. Perhaps the best option among free music processing programs. Everything you need is available in the program: sound recording, editing tools, effects package and file export in several popular formats: MP3, WAV, Ogg, FLAC, AIFF and AU. You can work on several tracks at once, which is rare for a free program. There are versions for Windows, Mac OS X and even Linux. In addition to the standard version for a computer, the software has a portable modification. Audacity Portable also allows you to edit audio, remove noise, apply effects and filters on mobile devices. Many users complain about not the most convenient interface of both Audacity, but this does not interfere with the basic tasks of working with sound. It has rich enough functionality for a free program, multiplatform, support for connecting external plug-ins and recording equipment.

Presentation tools for creating electronic slides to help illustrate a speaker's message are now increasingly media oriented. There is a large number of programs, with a range of visual and animation effects, ways to control presentations and a set of supported multimedia files to import as slide content. The presentation is an

information product that combines all multimedia formats into one. To create presentations, the user can use online platforms or use PC presentation software. There are many programs for creating presentations and we will look at some of them that are considered the best.

Apple Keynote is the most successful competitor to PowerPoint on macOS. This interactive presentation software allows you to create engaging and dynamic presentations, add charts and graphs, edit photos, and apply effects. You can access your presentations both online and offline using iCloud, the mobile app, or the PC version on Mac.

LibreOffice Impress offers drawing and diagramming tools to help you design your presentation. Animation and various effects will create an impressive and memorable presentation. The program is also available as an app, so your presentations will be available on other devices - in a smartphone or on a smart watch.

Adobe Spark is a graphic design and presentation tool that helps you create truly impressive slides. In Adobe Spark, you can upload your images, choose the desired format, icons and fonts. The program has several versions: Spark Post, Spark Page or Spark Video. Choose the right one based on your needs and goals.

SlideDog is a presentation creation program that allows you to create playlists from presentation files and easily switch between them. You can combine files in various formats, such as PDF, PowerPoint, web pages, and more. Other available features include real-time collaboration, interactive elements, and remote control from various devices to streamline the process.

Camtasia. A video presentation tool, great for recording screen movements, adjusting or editing videos, and importing videos from external sources. After finishing the editing process, you can export the video in the desired format. The program is available for both Windows and Mac.

Slides. The easy-to-use tool is designed for both simple and complex tasks and offers many features for editing and presenting. Thanks to advanced features, it is possible to view the source code of the project in HTML, CSS, Javascript, customize it, download a copy and present it online or offline. You can easily integrate Google

Sheets, Docs and Drive into the platform and even access your notes right on your mobile devices. The tool also includes analytics for more complex presentations.

Prezi offers a wide range of editable templates for creating interactive presentations. The tool is designed for both team and individual work, its functionality allows you to maximize the efficiency of the presentation creation process. Smart maps, unlimited zoom, interactive features, simplicity and convenience - that's what makes Prezi one of the most popular online presentation tools.

Google Slides is a free online presentation tool and one of the most popular Microsoft Word alternatives if you want to create PowerPoint presentations. You can create your presentation from scratch or choose one of the pre-made templates. Google Slides gives you the ability to create, edit, and share presentations from anywhere, anytime, on any device—phone, tablet, or computer. If you need to show your presentation offline, you can download it in a variety of formats, including PDF, PPT, or PPTX.

There is no single answer which tool or program for creating presentations is the best, because it all depends on your goals. All of the tools on the list are designed to simplify and streamline the presentation process and help users get the results they want. There are many options, the user will definitely find the right one and create a fascinating interactive presentation in the shortest possible time.

CONCLUSIONS

Multimedia technologies every day more and more penetrate into various spheres of human activity. In most cases, the use of multimedia content has had a positive impact on the intensification of human labor. Multimedia tools are used to improve the process of activities. The use of multimedia content in the labor process raises it to a qualitatively new level, positively affects the motivation of a person to work, increases the level of their viability and activity in choosing methods for solving the tasks they face. These are not only new technical means, but also new forms and methods of application to the process of activity. Due to the simultaneous impact of graphic, sound and visual information on a person, multimedia tools have a great emotional, spectacular charge. At the same time, thanks to the ability to visually, spectacularly

present information, multimedia allows you to implement the fundamental principle of visibility at a qualitatively new level.

Here are some key benefits of software related to multimedia editors.

- Comprehensive solution of user problems related to the production of multimedia content.

- Ability to work with different formats within the same information environment.

- Saving money for the purchase of specialized software products for working with certain types of content.

- Solving the problem of incompatibility of data formats.

- Saving time for specialists to download, upload, convert files.

- Multimedia editors often have sound and footage libraries, photobanks, templates, effects, and other collections of data in various formats. Thanks to this, the user saves time searching for elements for multimedia content, avoids the difficulties associated with copyright infringement, and does not spend money on photo/video/sound databank services.

Modern directions of development of software for working with multimedia:

- Multimedia editors depending on the purpose of use. For example, editors of multimedia presentations.

- Simple software products for mass production of multimedia content. For such programs, the needs are formed mainly from social networks and business.

- Software products for working with one type of data (text, photo, video) with the addition of functionality for other types of content or combining several editors for different formats in one interface.

- Multimedia editors, with a single environment for working with all data formats.

- Media editors for placing multimedia content on information platforms, as well as saving live media for further processing.

The listed directions are reflected in multimedia editors. They determine the vector for the further development of multimedia and show the functionality that will be implemented in the near future.

The prospects for multimedia are diverse, the areas of application will expand, among other things, due to the emergence of new information technologies and ways of processing information. The combination of multimedia with other technologies will contribute to their more dynamic development and even greater integration into all spheres of society.

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